

SafeHabitus

Deliverable 1.5

Understanding farm safety and farmer health challenges in the EU

Batch 1 of EIP-Agri Practice Abstracts

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Acronyms

The list of acronyms presented below is specific to the text presented in the introduction.

AKIS: Agricultural Knowledge Innovation System

CG: Core Group

CoP: Community of Practice

CT: Core Team

EU: European Union

FHS: Farm Health and Safety

FHS KIS: Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation System

GP: Good Practice

MAA: Multi-actor Approach

MSD: Musculoskeletal disorders

NGO: Non-governmental organisation / Non-profit organisation

PA: Practice Abstract

PNR: Farm Safety and Farmer Health Needs Register

PPE: Personal protective equipment

QH: Quadruple Helix

SH: SafeHabitus

SI: Social Innovation

TN: Technical Note

Acknowledgements

The knowledge presented in this Deliverable represents inputs from the 11 Community of Practice (CoP) partners in the SafeHabitus project. Each CoP is led by a project partner who, collectively, have brought together over 180 farm safety and farmer health experts in support of the development of the Practice Abstracts presented in this report. In addition to thanking the individual authors of the Practice Abstracts, we extend our heartfelt appreciation to the members of the CoPs who contributed their time, knowledge and expertise. Their support has resulted in the creation of knowledge that highlights the diversity of farm safety and farmer/worker health needs across the EU. They have also been instrumental in identifying priorities and good practices that address these challenges.

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Introduction

SafeHabitus is a multi-actor project that seeks to strengthen FHS KIS and support the EU transition to social sustainability in farming. The SafeHabitus approach recognises that whilst enhancing awareness and understanding of risks and hazards is one part of the solution, it is not the only, nor indeed the most effective solution to the health and safety challenge, particularly when many of the unsafe or unhealthy behaviours are habitual¹. Overcoming this challenge requires not only awareness raising regarding risks and hazards but also a systematic approach - one that has the farmer or worker at the centre, supported by the community of stakeholders who can support them to adopt safer and healthier practices².

This report provides an overview of the background, networks, and key safety challenges faced by farms in 11 EU member states who are represented by partners in the SafeHabitus consortium (Figure 1). The member states and associated partners were selected based on their capacity to implement the project activities and deliver the intended outputs, in addition to representing the diversity of EU agriculture. Six of the partners are drawn from the Sacurima Network, an EU Cost Action that completed its work in 2021 assessing the reasons why agriculture, is consistently amongst one of the most dangerous occupations in Europe and continually lags behind improvements made in occupational health and safety in other major economic sectors. The knowledge of this group and their understanding of the complexity of the challenge enabled SafeHabitus to start from an advanced position. This team is joined by institutions and businesses that function as knowledge brokers in the AKIS by working closely with farmers, policy stakeholders and researchers. This supports SafeHabitus to go beyond the state of the art by moving away from generic efforts to improve FHS amongst farmers and workers, and draw on the group's expertise to respond to end-user needs by developing practical innovations that encourage farmers to take action.

The aim of this report is to serve as an initial exploration of the safety issues in European agriculture and, more importantly, to collate potential solutions and good practices to address these safety challenges. This work will be expanded through ongoing and planned research and project activities that will be reported in the next two years.

¹ Kwasnicka, D., Dombrowski, S.U., White, M. and Sniehotta, F., 2016. Theoretical explanations for maintenance of behaviour change: a systematic review of behaviour theories. *Health Psychology Review*, 10(3), pp.277-296

² O'Connor, T., Kinsella, J., McNamara, J., O'Hora, D. and Meredith, D., 2021. Learning through design using collaborative Intervention Mapping with acceptability evaluation: the case of a group-based farm safety intervention. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 27(3), pp.403-420.

Figure 1. SafeHabitus Communities of Practice

Developing the Practice Abstracts

Work Package 2 of the SafeHabitus project implements a Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) through the establishment of 11 CoPs that engage 180 FHS actors and stakeholders to share knowledge, enhance understanding of the nature of farm safety challenges and support the co-creation of practical solutions to farm health and safety issues³. Following the establishment of the CoP, a ‘Needs Register’ was developed. The register not only details specific health and/or safety challenges but also identifies which populations are affected by these challenges and what actions are necessary to overcome them. The role of different groups of actors, e.g. farmers, farm advisors, policy makers, industry etc., in the development or implementation of actions is considered.

The work undertaken by each CoP to date is summarised in seven Technical Notes (TN) – see list below. These notes form the basis of this report and document the social, economic and policy context to farm safety, the establishment of the CoP, the identification of farm safety and farmer health issues, and the identification of good practices. A selection of these notes, i.e. those focused on specific health or safety needs and associated good practices, are presented in this report. The TNs were summarised using the EIP-AGRI/EU CAP Network Practice Abstract format, i.e. short articles of roughly 250 words focused on specific issues. The purpose of the PAs is to make the information collated and created by the CoPs accessible to a wide variety of end-users, particularly farm advisors and policy stakeholders.

Thematic Focus of SafeHabitus Practice Abstracts and Technical Notes

1. An overview of farming, farmers and workers, and health and safety issues in the CoP country. (TN)

³ For more information on the SH MAA see Annex 1 of Deliverable 2.1 *Baseline monitoring and evaluation report*

2. A description of the CoP, i.e. size, location, types of members, the broad focus/interest of the CoP. (TN)
3. An overview of the long list of issues and needs identified by the CoPs. (PA and TN)
4. Assessment of Critical issues and Critical Needs identified by the CoP: No. 1. (PA and TN)
5. Assessment of Critical issues and Critical Needs identified by the CoP: No. 2. (PA and TN)
6. Assessment of Critical issues and Critical Needs identified by the CoP: No. 3. (PA and TN)
7. Identification and description of relevant Good Practices that protect wellbeing or enhance quality of life. (PA and TN)

Taken collectively, the library of PAs and TNs represent a knowledge database that enables users to assess similarities and differences between the 11 CoP partners in terms of the size and structure of farming in their country/region and the level of farm injuries and fatalities (TN 1); the composition of their CoP (TN 2); the variety of safety and health challenges in their country (TN 3 and PA 3); details associated with three priority needs, including identification of potential good practices that will support the delivery of services or that can help farmers and farm workers adopt practices that improve their health, safety, or working conditions (TNs 4-6 and PAs 4 – 6); and, understanding and supporting the quality of life or wellbeing of farmers, farm workers and their communities (TN 7 and PA 7). It is important to note that we have kept the numbering of TNs and PAs consistent, e.g. PA3 = TN3, in order to maintain the link between the summary and longer notes.

Terminology

As SafeHabitus is primarily concerned with people working on farms, it is unsurprising that two common concepts are repeated throughout the PAs, i.e. farms and, particularly, different groups of people who work on farms. The diversity of terms used to describe farm workers in the EU reflects cultural, linguistic, and structural differences across member states. In English, "farmer" is a common, catch-all term, while "agricultural worker" often refers specifically to employed labourers rather than farm owners. In France, "agriculteur" and "exploitant agricole" emphasise agricultural production and farm operation, while "ouvrier agricole" denotes employees. Germany distinguishes "Landwirt" (farm manager/owner) from "Landarbeiter" (farm labourer). In Spain, "agricultor" and "campesino" carry cultural connotations of farming identity, with "trabajador agrícola" reserved for hired labour. Eastern European countries like Poland use "rolnik" for traditional family farmers, while newer terms like "pracownik rolny" highlight hired workers. Differences also arise in recognition of gender or small-scale farming, such as "contadina" in Italy. These linguistic distinctions underscore the varying roles, traditions, and perceptions of farming across the EU, complicating policy standardisation and cross-border collaboration.

As a multi-actor project SafeHabitus was conscious of the need to engage a wide variety of actors with a variety of expertise. In order to facilitate knowledge exchange at the national level, we did not seek to impose a taxonomy or standard referencing system on partners or the CoP participants. Rather, we sought to fit the concepts and terminology that is presented in the PAs and TNs, within the Eurostat framework describing the agricultural workforce. This led to the identification of four groups (Figure 2). Whilst these are presented as distinct groups, it is important to note that when it comes to family farms, i.e. those farms mainly owned and operated by family labour, there can be significant overlap between groups.

1. Persons who are legally and economically responsible for the farm and/or farm management and/or as a part of farm family exposed to the farm health and safety risks. In the PAs these people are variously referred to as: farmer, self-employed farmer, farm holder,

farm owner, farm manager (farm manager can be also a person with a written contract and in that case belongs to Group 2), co-owner, joint owner, partner, spouse, family (some family members can also belong to Group 3, i.e. vulnerable populations).

2. Persons who have a written contract for employment. These persons are categorised into the separate group as their position, rights and duties are different from the Group 1. They are also often treated differently in farm health and safety systems than farm holders despite the fact that they share the same workplace and many of the same tasks. In the texts people in this group are referred to as farm worker, employee, worker, employed worker, salaried worker, or hired worker.

3. Vulnerable population covers a wide variety of workers ranging from foreign-born farm workers, migrant and seasonal farm workers; beginning farmers (those with <5 years of experience); members of farm families (including women, children, and older adults); and farmers and farmworkers with physical, mental health, or intellectual disabilities⁴

4. A group of people who occasionally work on farm and are exposed to the health and safety risks but are not employed by the holding. They may be self-employed or employed by another employer, e.g. veterinarian, semiologist, farm relief worker.

⁴ Ramos, A.K., Girdžiūtė, L., Starič, J. & Rautiainen, R.H. 2021. Identifying "Vulnerable Agricultural Populations" at Risk for Occupational Injuries and Illnesses: A European Perspective. JOURNAL OF AGROMEDICINE 2021, VOL. 26, NO. 3, 340–345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2020.1771498>

People on farm – who is exposed to health and safety risks on farms. Modified and derived from the Eurostat definitions. Source: Eurostat, Statistics Explained.

Figure 2. Key actors on farms. Modified and derived from the Eurostat ⁵

⁵ Eurostat. Eurostat. Statistics Explained. Category: Agriculture glossary. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Category:Agriculture_glossary. Cited 22nd November 2024.

SafeHabitus

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

SafeHabitus: An overview

Farming is the most hazardous occupation in Europe with European statistics showing a 233% higher fatality rate and 18% higher accident rate compared to other industries. SafeHabitus aims to make farming safer by applying an innovative, participatory, and collaborative approach to Farm Health and Safety (FHS). We apply a multi-actor process to strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation Systems (FHS KIS) and support the European transition to social sustainability in farming.

The project comprises 20 partners from across Europe and runs from 2023 – 2026. The logic underpinning the project is that improving FHS is about more than providing farmers with information: improving FHS requires action by a range of stakeholders to empower and support farmers, their families and farm workers by adopting new, safer and healthier ways of working. SafeHabitus seeks to identify or develop good practices that are tailored to the particular needs of farmers working in different social, cultural and economic contexts across the EU, and share these with end users. SafeHabitus adopts a place-based multi-actor approach that promotes a comprehensive and multi-level strategy, i.e. local/regional to EU, to address FHS at every level.

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Target audience

Target group 1: Farmers, farm workers and others exposed to the farm environment

Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Policymakers, policy stakeholders

Figure 3. SafeHabitus consortium

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Estonia

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: Farming is one of the most traditional yet hazardous professions in Estonia, ranking fourth in occupational danger. Challenges such as inadequate occupational safety data, resource shortages, and ineffective implementation of safety regulations contribute to a false perception of safety. Farmers and workers often underestimate workplace risks, and many lack awareness of occupational safety measures.

Method: The Estonian Community of Practice (EstCoP) developed a Farm Health and Safety Needs Register using a three-step process. First, they analysed agricultural accident statistics to identify key risks. Second, members completed surveys highlighting priority issues. Finally, discussions summarised the findings and prioritised actions. The process addressed systemic, cultural, and practical barriers to farm safety and health.

Results: The EstCoP identified key needs, including improved livestock handling practices, safer farm vehicle design, better facilities, and enhanced worker safety measures. They emphasised the importance of addressing mental health and work organisation issues. Proposed solutions focus on tailored education and training initiatives, early integration of safety topics into agricultural curricula, and farmer-centred advisory services to improve safety awareness and practices. A shift in attitudes toward occupational safety, supported by early education and farmer-centred advisory services, is critical to improving farm safety and health in Estonia.

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Target audience

Target group 1: Policymakers,
policy stakeholders

Target group 2: Advisors,
innovation support services

Target group 3: Teachers, trainers,
students

Enhancing safety in livestock farming: handling, facilities, and human-animal relations

Issue: Work accidents in agriculture, particularly in livestock farming, remain a significant challenge in Estonia. Handling livestock such as cattle, pigs, and horses poses dangers due to unexpected animal behaviour, while inadequate facilities and training increase the likelihood of injuries. Vulnerable groups, including elderly farmers, young or inexperienced workers, and seasonal labourers, are particularly at risk.

Method: Targeted inspections of agricultural enterprises in 2023 by the Estonian Labour Inspectorate highlighted the importance of effective risk analysis, employee training, and safer infrastructure. Training programmes on animal handling, emergency response, and ongoing education were prioritised. Facility upgrades, such as non-slip flooring and ergonomic tools, and mental health support were also introduced.

Results: Strategies include mandatory training programmes on animal handling and emergency response. For policy development and enforcement, stricter regulations, regular inspections, and health checks are essential. Infrastructure and facility improvements, such as non-slip flooring and better ergonomics, will reduce hazards. Health monitoring and disease prevention, including regular health checks and enhanced mental health support, are vital. Lastly, developing community and support networks to share best practices and provide emotional support will strengthen the farming community and improve safety.

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Target audience

Target group 1: Advisors,
innovation support services

Target group 2: Teachers, trainers,
students

Target group 3: Policymakers,
policy stakeholders

Supporting farm work environment risk assessment and management

Issue: Agricultural work in Estonia poses significant occupational risks, including machinery accidents, slips, and unpredictable animal behaviour. These risks are often linked to inadequate risk assessments, outdated safety practices, and limited training. Despite a reduction in reported occupational accidents, this trend reflects changes in reporting practices rather than an actual decline in incidents, with serious and moderate accidents still prevalent.

Method: The Labour Inspectorate of Estonia inspected 80 agricultural enterprises in May 2023, identifying 584 deficiencies in risk analysis, safety instructions, training, personal protective equipment (PPE), health checks, and compliance with work and rest time regulations. To address these issues, Estonia developed a digital risk assessment tool, enabling companies to identify and mitigate workplace risks efficiently.

Results: The inspections emphasised the need for accurate and up-to-date risk analyses, proper training, and compliance with safety protocols. The digital tool supports companies in creating action plans to improve safety. Recommendations include maintaining regular risk assessments, providing proper PPE and training, ensuring first aid preparedness, and adhering to working time regulations. These measures help prevent workplace injuries and foster a safer, healthier agricultural work environment.

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Target audience

Target group 1: Advisors,
innovation support services
Target group 2: Public authorities,
rural development organisations
Target group 3: Policymakers,
policy stakeholders

Networking to improve the Farm Safety and Farm Health Knowledge and Innovation System (FHS KIS)

Issue: Farmers and agricultural workers in Estonia face significant health and safety challenges. Despite these risks, communication between stakeholders is limited, and the sector lacks a unified approach to addressing occupational health and safety (OHS). Farmers often struggle to voice their concerns publicly, and researchers face difficulties identifying and engaging relevant stakeholders.

Method: The Estonian Communities of Practice (EstCoP) initiative brings together farmers, researchers, public institutions, and private organisations to improve collaboration and communication. The network addresses OHS challenges by fostering partnerships, raising awareness, and sharing knowledge. Stakeholders include ministries, farmer unions, labour organisations, educational institutions, and media. Key activities include risk assessment, training programmes, and promoting tools like the OIRA risk management e-tool.

Results: The EstCoP initiative demonstrates the value of a collaborative, bottom-up approach. Farmers identify critical safety issues, which are analysed and addressed through research, policy, and practical solutions. Networking activities have increased risk awareness, improved safety training, and supported the implementation of preventive measures. Collaboration across stakeholder groups ensures initiatives are tailored to the agricultural context, enhancing workplace safety and reducing occupational injuries and illnesses.

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Target audience

Target group 1: Researchers
Target group 2: Public authorities,
rural development organisations
Target group 3: Policymakers,
policy stakeholders

Improving quality of life and farm viability: a dairy farm case study

Issue: Dairy farming in Estonia faces challenges such as decreasing agricultural land, urban sprawl, and the need for better working conditions and safety in farms. Attracting workers to rural areas and ensuring the wellbeing of both animals and employees are critical for sustaining productivity and improving farm viability.

Methods: Varudi Manor Dairy Farm serves as an example of addressing these challenges through strategic investment and modernisation. Beginning with 50 cows in the 1990s, the farm expanded under new management in 2013, growing to 600 cows and 600 hectares of land. Investments included a noiseless Fullwood milking parlour, ergonomically adjustable workspaces, and systems for animal comfort, such as scratching brushes and heated utility rooms. Financial support from PRIA and careful loan management enabled these developments.

Results: The modernisation improved both animal welfare and employee working conditions. Stress-free environments for cows resulted in higher-quality milk, while ergonomic facilities and innovative practices created a safer and more attractive workplace. The farm demonstrates how investments in technology and wellbeing can ensure sustainable growth, support workers, and meet modern agricultural demands. Varudi Manor is a model of how farms can balance productivity with quality of life.

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Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Finland

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: Finnish farming faces safety and health challenges despite a long-term decline in injury rates. Farmers and agricultural workers are still at risk of injury, disease, and mental health issues. The unique Arctic farming conditions, combined with machinery use, animal handling, and long working hours, create a hazardous work environment. Attitudes towards safety, underestimation of risks, and weaknesses in communication further hinder safety improvements on farms. In addition, the amount of labourer in Finnish farms is quite low which means that many tasks are done alone.

Method: A systematic approach was used to develop a Farm Safety and Farmer Health Needs Register (PNR) through the Finnish Community of Practice (FinCoP). Input from stakeholders, including farmers, experts, and policymakers, was gathered via workshops, data collection, and community assessments. Identified needs were categorised into two main themes: (1) Physical, Chemical, and Biological Injuries, and (2) Health Risks. Priority areas included Arctic farming safety, machinery use, personal protective equipment (PPE), mental wellbeing, work-related stress, and communication between farmers and farm workers.

Results: The PNR highlights critical needs such as enhanced safety training, PPE support, risk management tools, and measures to address mental health issues. It underscores the need for targeted communication to shift farming culture towards safer practices. Collaborative efforts among farmers, researchers, and policymakers are essential to improve farm safety and health.

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Target group 3: Teachers, trainers, students

Farm safety videos

Issue: Accidents on farms remain a serious concern. Despite prevention efforts, compliance with farm safety rules is difficult to maintain. Farmers' attitudes towards safety are shaped by cultural factors, social roles, and lifelong learning. Younger generations, exposed to modern tools and media, may see safety from a fresh perspective. Promoting a safety-first culture requires innovative approaches that engage young people.

Method: To address this challenge, Mela, the Finnish Farmers' Social Insurance Institution, launched the "Smart Farm Videos" competition. This initiative invites agricultural students to create short videos about farm safety. The process involves students researching, scripting, and filming safety concepts, which helps them internalise key safety messages. Winning videos are showcased at award ceremonies and shared on social media, educational platforms, and industry websites.

Results: The competition has run twice and is now a regular event. It has attracted over 100 student participants, and the resulting videos have been praised by both educators and farmers. The 2023 winning video, created by Janina Sivonen, focused on the importance of cattle handling skills to reduce accidents on dairy farms. The competition strengthens cooperation between Mela and educational institutions, and several schools have integrated it into their curriculum. Mela's experience highlights how video production can promote farm safety in an engaging and accessible way.

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Supporting farmer wellbeing with the work ability tool

Issue: Farmers often face challenges in balancing work demands with personal resources, increasing their risk of declining work ability. Dairy farmers, in particular, experience a high prevalence of reduced work ability, with steeper declines for women over 40. Factors such as physical and mental strain, repetitive tasks, and limited recovery time contribute to these issues.

Method: The Finnish Farmers' Social Insurance Institution (Mela) developed the Farmer's Work Ability Scale tool to help farmers detect and address risks to their work ability early. The tool uses ten targeted questions to assess work ability, wellbeing, and safety at work. It provides personalised feedback and connects farmers to Mela's work ability services. Respondents can compare their results with peers based on age, gender, and production type.

Results: Since its launch in 2022, the tool has been used 3,631 times, with dairy, cereal, and beef farmers as key users. It has gained international recognition, including being granted an honorary award from the International Social Security Association. Future plans include developing training sessions based on the tool.

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Target group 3: Advisors, innovation support services

Supporting farmers' health with preventive occupational services

Issue: Farmers and farm workers face significant health risks from occupational hazards such as dust, noise, and chemicals. In Finland, employers must provide preventive occupational health care for their hired workers. Occupational health (OH) care is available also for farm entrepreneurs, but on voluntary basis.

Method: Farmers' occupational health service (FOHS) provides a preventive approach to improving farmers' work ability, health and safety. Services include farm workplace surveys, health checks, and support for rehabilitation. A farm-specific action plan is developed with the farmer, and a team of occupational health professionals conducts the services. Recommendations focus on reducing hazards, improving ergonomics, and promoting safe practices. FOHS is subsidised, with certain preventive services provided at no cost up to an annual limit.

Results: Studies show that FOHS has positive effects on farmers' work ability but no direct link to reduced injury risk. Uptake remains low among part-time farmers, highlighting a need for tailored outreach.

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Target group 2: Policymakers, policy stakeholders

Target group 3: Health service providers

Supporting farmers' wellbeing through holiday and stand-in services

Issue: Livestock farming is demanding and leaves little time for rest or family. Farmers need a break to support their wellbeing and balance work with their personal lives. However, the demanding nature of farming can make it hard to step away from daily tasks.

Method: Farmers' Holiday and Stand-In Scheme allows full-time livestock farmers to take annual leave or access stand-in help during sickness, parental leave, or other necessary circumstances. Relief workers, trained in agriculture, handle animal care and farm tasks during the farmer's absence. The scheme is supported by the Finnish Ministry of Social Affairs and Health and The Finnish Farmers' Social Insurance Institution (Mela) and coordinated locally by 12 municipal units.

Results: In 2023, 11,595 farmers used holiday services, and 3,560 accessed stand-in services. The scheme enhances farmers' ability to cope with work demands, supports family life, and ensures ethical animal care. However, challenges remain, such as labour shortages, high sick-leave rates of relief workers, and the need for better workplace safety. Ongoing efforts include piloting work coaching and improving practices on joint work places.

Recommendation: Enhancing working conditions for relief workers and fostering collaboration between farmers and local units are essential for the future of the scheme.

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Target group 3: Public authorities, rural development organisations

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP France

Farmer health and farm safety needs in France

Issue: Farming in France presents significant health and safety challenges due to the physically demanding nature of the work, including risks from animal handling and machinery causing musculoskeletal disorders. Mental health concerns linked to stress and fatigue are also prevalent, with a notably high suicide rate among farmers. The decrease in the number of farmers and the increasingly larger farms further exacerbate these issues.

Method: The SafeHabitus Community of Practice (CoP) in France collected data through expert interviews, including with the MSA Statistics department, and semi-structured interviews with key agricultural stakeholders. Existing statistical data from MSA and Eurostat were analysed to identify priority concerns. A CoP kick-off meeting was held to discuss health and safety challenges for farm workers.

Results: The CoP identified several key issues, including the high rate of accidents in livestock farming, the importance of mental health, and the need for better ergonomic considerations. Proposed solutions mentioned by stakeholders include training for animal handling, improving farm workstation design and raising awareness of mental health and available support structures. The CoP's work highlights the need for collaborative approaches to enhancing safety and wellbeing in agriculture for physical and mental health risks.

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Overcoming the workload challenge in farming – Work Assessment Method (WAM)

Issue: Farming is a demanding occupation, and farmers face significant challenges due to heavy workloads, long hours and the risk of accidents. Heavy workloads can also increase stress and mental health issues, contributing to the high rate of suicides among farmers. Many farmers struggle to manage their tasks effectively, which impacts both their wellbeing and farm productivity.

Method: The Work Assessment Method (WAM), developed by INRAE and the French Livestock Institute, is a method designed to assess the workload and time requirements of for the inputs in terms of human resources. The tool helps farmers evaluate how routine and seasonal tasks are organised. The WAM gathers both qualitative and quantitative data through a semi-structured survey, considering the availability and skills of workers, as well as seasonal variations in work. The data are then used to create a detailed workload report for the farm and engage in discussions with the farm's manager and workers about them.

Results: The WAM provides a comprehensive overview of a farm's workload, highlighting areas for improvement. It allows farmers to benchmark their current situation against similar systems, organisations, and operations, and identify practical steps to enhance the organisation of the work. The results can also support strategic planning for generational renewal, improve decision-making, and help farmers balance work demands with professional and personal time, leading to better overall farm sustainability and farmer wellbeing.

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Tackling psychosocial risks and mental health in farming - initiatives supporting farmers

Issue: Psychosocial risks (PSR) in farming, including stress, harassment, and isolation, significantly affect the mental and physical health of farmers. Long working hours, high pressures, and negative media portrayals contribute to anxiety, burnout, and a high risk of suicide. In France, suicides account for a significant percentage of farmers' causes of death.

Method: To address these risks, multiple initiatives have been implemented at various levels. Primary prevention efforts include raising awareness among farmers and advisors through film-debates and comic strips for instance. Secondary-level actions involve training a network of 'sentinels' (ie. monitors) to identify signs of psychological distress among farmers, who are able to bring them to the attention of those who can help. Tertiary support includes services such as the 'Agri Collectif' platform, distress hotlines, and respite schemes to offer psychological and practical support to farmers in need.

Results: These initiatives help to raise awareness of the psychosocial risks, provide early intervention, and offer resources for managing mental health challenges in farming. Networks and platforms connecting farmers to support services are crucial in addressing distress and preventing further mental health deterioration, and improving overall wellbeing in the sector.

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Reducing and managing musculoskeletal injuries in farming

Issue: Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are the leading cause of occupational illnesses in agriculture, affecting both farm managers and employees. These injuries result from a combination of things such as: physical strain, poorly designed workplaces or tools, bad habits, poor work organisation, repetitive movements, vibrations, etc. Musculoskeletal troubles cause joint pain and possibly chronic injuries; they are accentuated by the carrying of heavy loads or vibrations.

Method: Several initiatives have been launched to address MSDs including the use of exoskeletons during milking tasks, for example, as currently piloted in the “Exotraite” project under implementation in Normandy. In this project, three models were tested on dairy farms to help reduce physical strain during milking. The trials were supervised by prevention advisors and occupational physicians from the Agricultural Social Mutual Organisation (MSA).

Results: The “Exotraite” project has highlighted the potential benefits of exoskeletons in reducing physical loads and preventing MSDs. However, their use also raised concerns about increased mental strain, spinal pressure, and complications when interacting with livestock. Recommendations for farmers before buying such equipment include conducting thorough workstation analyses to correct any faults in milking parlour design or working posture, undergoing medical examinations, and testing equipment at least a month before purchase. Proper support and training are crucial to maximising the benefits of exoskeletons while minimising the risks.

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Supporting risk management on farms—an introduction to the occupational risk assessment document

Issue: Farm work presents a variety of risks, including injuries caused by animals, machinery, and worksite conditions. Musculoskeletal injuries are particularly common. Despite this, many farmers do not take account of the importance of identifying and managing risks.

Method: The Occupational Risk Assessment Document (DUERP) is a French regulation requiring farm employers to assess and document workplace risks. The DUERP helps farmers identify risks in their daily operations, including those from animals, equipment, and the work environment. It is updated annually or whenever significant changes are made to the farm's production system.

Results: The DUERP provides a comprehensive overview of a farm's risks, with a view to preventing and reducing them. It encourages discussion among farm workers and improves collaboration for identifying practical solutions. The DUERP must meet regulatory requirements; its implementation can be supported by training delivered by external experts, for example. Despite the challenges, the DUERP remains a valuable tool for improving farm safety and reducing accidents.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Germany

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: Agriculture in Germany faces significant occupational health and safety (OHS) challenges, with risks such as accidents in cattle husbandry, tractor operations, and exposure to health hazards like UV radiation and noise. These issues are exacerbated by changing climate conditions and the use of machinery with deficiencies in technical safety.

Method: The Occupational Risk Assessment Document, following the EU EIP AGRI format, uses data from the Social Insurance for Agriculture, Forestry and Horticulture (SVLFG) accident database to identify priority health and safety needs. It focuses on three key categories: cattle husbandry, tractors and agricultural machinery, and health hazards. Specific critical issues, such as cattle handling accidents and tractor-related injuries, are analysed, and potential solutions are explored.

Results: The report recommends prioritising technical safety measures, such as retrofitting equipment and improving machinery standards, alongside promoting driver safety training. It also calls for practical training to raise awareness of animal behaviour in cattle husbandry and initiatives to tackle health risks, including heat stress and musculoskeletal disorders. These solutions aim to reduce accidents and improve the overall health and safety of people working in agriculture.

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Enhancing safety - cattle farming

Issue: Cattle farming presents significant safety risks, with over a quarter of work-related accidents in agriculture occurring in animal husbandry. Increasing herd sizes and labour shortages have led farmers to rely more on bulls running in the herd for natural insemination, which increases the risk of accidents.

Method: Common accident causes include inadequate facilities, poor lighting and a lack of knowledge regarding cattle behaviour. Key risks arise from handling cattle, particularly during calving, working with bulls, and managing animals in pasture settings. Data from the SVLFG help identify critical factors contributing to these accidents.

Results: Recommendations include training farmers on safe cattle handling and recognising natural animal behaviour, improving technical equipment to reduce direct contact with animals, and enhancing stable design. These solutions can reduce the risk of accidents and improve safety, especially in small family farms, through tailored prevention measures.

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Enhancing safety - tractors and machinery

Issue: Tractors and agricultural machinery are essential in farming but pose significant safety risks. In Germany, fatal accidents involving tractors account for more than 10% of all agricultural accidents, despite falling rates across all tractor accidents. Accidents in common traffic and during operation should also be noted. Outdated, unsafe machinery and imported low-standard tractors exacerbate the problem.

Method: The approach focuses on improving both the technical safety of machinery and the operator's handling skills. Recommendations include the retrofitting of safe technology, the introduction of ergonomic safety features, and the development of smarter systems to prevent accidents. Operator training is also crucial to ensuring safe usage of machinery, particularly in recognising, managing and neutralising potential hazards.

Results: Improvements include better safety design for tractor ascents and seatbelt systems, compliance with EU safety standards for imported machinery, mandatory operator qualifications for risky tasks like chainsaw use. These measures aim to reduce accidents, with a focus on technical safety, especially on imported and outdated machinery. Regular safety training and awareness campaigns for operators are recommended to ensure safe practices and to ultimately prevent accidents from happening in the first place.

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Enhancing safety - occupational diseases and health hazards

Issue: Workers in the green sector, particularly in agriculture, face numerous health risks due to their exposure to ever-changing and unpredictable environmental and weather conditions as well as the nature of the work itself. Climate change, UV radiation, dusty environments, and noisy machinery contribute to skin cancer, respiratory diseases, hearing loss, and musculoskeletal disorders. Zoonotic diseases, such as Lyme disease, and mental health challenges, like stress and burnout, further exacerbate the situation.

Method: In Germany, occupational diseases are determined and recognised in a statutory procedure that requires the documentation/compilation of medical reports and insurance claims. Those in the green sector affected by these diseases are entitled to benefits such as medical treatments and financial support so long as they are insured. SVLFG plays a key role in supporting farmers by providing tailored preventive measures. These include providing personal protective equipment to reduce exposure to harmful elements, as well as offering training to help workers implement safety practices. Additionally, SVLFG promotes the use of ergonomic equipment to prevent musculoskeletal disorders and has been working on initiatives aimed at reducing noise levels of machinery to prevent hearing loss.

Results: Skin diseases, respiratory issues, and musculoskeletal disorders are the most common occupational diseases in the green sector. The preventive measures provided by SVLFG, such as the use of PPE, noise-reduced machinery, and ergonomic equipment, help to reduce these risks. Mental health is also supported through accessible counselling and stress management programmes. It is clear that the sector needs to put a priority on the adoption of preventive technical and organisational measures to reduce and ultimately eliminate all together the elements, items and circumstances that lead to degenerative health issues. In parallel, farmers need to take action to apply personal protective measures as a complement to these efforts.

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Overview of good practices supporting improvements in farmers' and farm workers' quality of life

Issue: Agriculture faces significant health and safety challenges, particularly for those working on farms. The respective core problems include high risks associated with animal husbandry (especially cattle farming), the use of machinery and exposure to health hazards that can lead to occupational diseases. Due to its particular working environment, socio-cultural and economic conditions, the agricultural sector faces specific challenges in implementing occupational health and safety.

Method: SVLFG has developed a variety of good practices to address these challenges. These include specialised and tailored training programmes (for example, on safe cattle handling), driver safety courses, the retrofitting of outdated machinery, and AI-supported camera systems for farm vehicles and machines. Additional initiatives include providing specialised support to seasonal workers, offering health protection measures and training, and mental health support.

Results: These measures have proven effective for improving health and safety in the green sector. Safety training and equipment retrofitting have contributed to reducing accidents, while mental health initiatives such as the creation of a crisis hotline and customised online health training modules, have been helping to improve farmers' overall wellbeing. These approaches attest to the fact that by adapting legislation, by providing targeted and customised support and by integrating modern technologies into the green sector, farmers' lives and overall quality of life can be significantly improved.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Ireland

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: Farming in Ireland plays a crucial role in the national economy but is associated with high rates of injury and death. These safety issues not only affect farmers and their families but also influence the sector's future, rural development, and food security. Bridging the gap between farmers' experiences with safety challenges and policymakers' approaches is critical. Challenges such as unsafe farm vehicles, inadequate facilities, mental health concerns, and poor work organisation contribute to high risks in farm health and safety (FHS), highlighting the need for a bottom-up approach.

Method: The Irish Community of Safe Farm Practice (IRL-CoP) created a Farm Safety and Health Needs Register, using data from Ireland's occupational safety surveillance system. The process involved discussions with stakeholders to identify risks and challenges in farm safety and health. These discussions highlighted specific needs related to machinery safety, livestock handling, mental health, and the safety of vulnerable groups like children and older farmers. The needs register also took into account cultural and social factors influencing farm safety practices.

Results: The IRL-CoP identified key solutions to address these needs, focusing on partnerships, education, policy, and research. Recommendations include improving farm machinery safety, developing tailored training programmes, and updating safety communications for different farming demographics. Solutions will prioritise farmer engagement, ensuring they are practical, culturally sensitive, and tailored to the realities of farming life. These measures aim to improve farm safety outcomes and reduce risks across Ireland's farming communities.

COP Ireland

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Target audience

Target group 1: Policymakers, policy stakeholders

Target group 2: Researchers

Target group 3: Teachers, trainers, students

Safer tractor drivers - understanding risks of blind spots and speed

Issue: Farming is a high-risk occupation, with tractor accidents accounting for a significant proportion of fatalities. Between 2011 and 2020, 55% of farm-related deaths were caused by tractor incidents, with vulnerable populations such as children and older farmers being particularly at risk.

Method: A 'train the trainer' approach was developed through the BeSafe for Tractor Operations (BTO) intervention, targeting farmers, especially older farmers. BTO included a 3-hour training session focused on raising awareness of tractor blind spots and the risks associated with stopping distances. Participants engaged in hands-on demonstrations and discussions, and received a demonstration kit to share the knowledge with family members, workers, and neighbours.

Results: The intervention successfully raised awareness of tractor blind spots and the importance of stopping distances. After completing the training, most farmers recognised the need to demonstrate these safety practices on their own farms. The 'train the trainer' model proved highly effective, with 90% of participants training others, reaching a wide audience of farm workers and family members. The success of BTO highlights the value of practical, peer-to-peer safety training and its potential for broader adoption of safer farming practices. Further development of tractor safety training should address additional risks such as safe tractor entry/exit and the health impacts of noise and vibration.

COP Ireland

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Target audience

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Target group 3: Researchers

Increasing awareness of farm safety risks among children

Issue: Farming is the most dangerous occupation in Ireland, with the highest rate of workplace fatalities. This risk extends beyond farmers, as farms are often family homes, exposing children and non-farmers to potential harm. Between 2011 and 2021, 21 children lost their lives on Irish farms, most often due to accidents involving tractors and machinery. Many children are exposed to risks on farms, where safety awareness is often insufficient, and a culture of normalising danger prevails.

Method: AgriKids™ was established in 2014 to address child safety on farms. The programme engages children through educational resources such as storybooks, workbooks, digital games, and workshops. These resources aim to teach children about farm safety, empower them as safety ambassadors, and encourage them to share safety messages with their families and communities.

Results: AgriKids™ has successfully raised awareness of farm safety among children, helping to shift the safety culture on farms. Children are now more aware of the dangers and are influencing their families to adopt safer behaviours. The programme has led to greater engagement from schools and communities. Future efforts will focus on increasing childcare options in rural areas, integrating farm safety into educational curricula, and challenging the normalisation of risky behaviour on farms.

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Target audience

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Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Teachers, trainers, students

Supporting farmers' cardiovascular health: Farmers Have Hearts – Cardiovascular Health Programme

Issue: Farmers face significant cardiovascular health risks. Three in four farmers have multiple cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk factors, which increase the likelihood of acute cardiac events. CVD is a major cause of disability among farm operators and contributes to higher accident risk, and lower farm productivity and income. Mortality statistics indicate that Irish farmers have 2.5 times higher mortality from heart disease compared to other occupation groups.

Method: The Farmers Have Hearts – Cardiovascular Health Programme (FHH-CHP) addressed these risks by providing culturally competent and tailored support. Farmers took part in workplace health checks at livestock marts and agri-branches. Farmers received tailored lifestyle advice, with options for mobile health text messages or phone coaching to support lifestyle changes.

Results: By the end of the programme, 41.2% of farmers improved their cardiovascular risk profiles, with those taking part in lifestyle support interventions gaining significantly higher improvements. Most farmers reported making sustainable lifestyle changes, particularly in diet and physical activity. The programme demonstrated the effectiveness of tailored, farmer-centred approaches in promoting long-term health improvements.

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Target audience

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Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Policymakers, policy stakeholders

EIP-AGRI projects on farm health, safety, and wellbeing in Ireland

Issue: Agriculture in Ireland is the most dangerous profession, with high fatality rates mainly caused by machinery and large livestock. Farmers also face mental health challenges like stress and sleep issues, worsened by a cultural stigma against seeking help. Further research is needed to understand the impact of these risks on farm families, which make up 99% of Irish farms.

Method: The European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) Scheme funds local, bottom-up projects addressing farm health, safety, and wellbeing. Eight EIP-funded projects in Ireland co-designed initiatives targeting farm safety, mental health, and family wellbeing. Farmers were directly involved in decision-making, ensuring their perspectives shaped project design and implementation. These projects engaged farmers, researchers, and community organisations, with funding covering up to 100% of costs. Projects were evaluated for scalability and effectiveness.

Results: The projects improved farmers' knowledge of health, safety, and wellbeing practices. Initiatives like FarmConnect and Embrace FARM's Encircle Programme supported farmers and families through training, emotional support, and resources. However, challenges in impact measurement and engagement highlight the need for more rigorous evaluations. Future success requires tailored approaches, sustainable funding, greater farmer involvement in development, and a centralised hub for best practices to expand these initiatives across the EU.

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Target audience

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Target group 3: Policymakers, policy stakeholders

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Lithuania

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: In Lithuania, agriculture remains a high-risk sector for accidents and occupational diseases. Despite a significant portion of farm workers being self-employed, accidents remain frequent, with 3.6 fatalities and 7 serious non-fatal accidents recorded annually. Key hazards include machinery maintenance, animal handling, and physical health risks, such as noise and vibration. Additionally, self-employed farmers and their family members are often excluded from safety monitoring systems.

Method: A priority needs register was created based on accident statistics and expert insights. The focus was on understanding the causes of accidents, including improper machinery maintenance, inadequate animal handling, and physical health hazards. Recommendations were developed to improve safety practices and raise awareness among farmers, their families, and farm workers.

Results: To address these issues, a systematic approach is essential, involving all stakeholders, including farmers, organisations, and state institutions. Raising awareness through safety training and better communication can improve safety standards. Furthermore, promoting participation in safety programmes and developing initiatives that encourage farm safety could lead to a safer and healthier farming environment, especially on small farms.

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Target audience

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Target group 3: Advisors,
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Maintenance of machinery, equipment, and buildings in agriculture: challenges and solutions

Issue: In Lithuania, agricultural accidents often result from inadequate maintenance of machinery, equipment, and buildings. Unsafe practices, lack of professional skills, and insufficient safety awareness contribute to these incidents, with 20–30% of accidents linked to unsafe maintenance.

Method: The issue was analysed through accident reports and discussions in the Community of Practice. This approach identified the common causes of accidents, such as insufficient training, lack of safety knowledge, and poor maintenance practices, particularly on small farms.

Results: To address these challenges, key recommendations for adoption include the following: improving safety management, providing continuous training, raising awareness of maintenance risks, and ensuring the proper use of personal protective equipment. Additionally, technical improvements and financial support for small farms are necessary to upgrade equipment and enhance safety standards.

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Target group 2: Farmers, farm
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Target group 3: Teachers, trainers,
students

Enhancing safety – optimising handling practices, facilities, and human-animal relations in livestock farming

Issue: Animal handling in livestock farming presents significant safety risks, including animal behaviour (e.g., kicking), handler negligence, and hazards in farm facilities. In Lithuania, a high number of accidents in agriculture are linked to animal husbandry, with the most critical causes being unsafe handling practices, inadequate infrastructure, and employee complacency due to routine tasks.

Method: Evidence drawn from accident reports, expert assessments, and data from the State Labour Inspectorate, identifies key hazards in cattle handling, including unsafe work practices, inadequate knowledge of animal behaviour, and poor facility conditions leading to slips, trips, and falls.

Results: Key recommendations for enhancing safety include providing training on animal behaviour, improving safety standards for facilities, ensuring proper maintenance of infrastructure, and avoiding solo animal handling. Additionally, integrating safety practices into educational programmes, focusing on both small and large farms, and promoting peer support among workers are essential steps for reducing accidents and improving overall safety in animal husbandry.

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Understanding and tackling occupational diseases and health hazards in agriculture

Issue: Agricultural workers are exposed to physical and ergonomic risks, leading to high rates of occupational diseases, particularly musculoskeletal disorders and noise-induced hearing loss. These issues are prevalent in Lithuania, with workers exposed to physical risks over long periods, especially on small family farms. Insufficient attention to safety measures and outdated equipment contribute to these health hazards.

Method: A multifaceted approach has been employed, including continuous risk assessments, educational campaigns, and farmers' advisory services. The State Labour Inspectorate, along with other organisations, work to raise awareness, conduct inspections, and provide tools for managing physical risks. Financial support for equipment renewal and personal protective gear is also offered.

Results: The initiative has helped to raise awareness and implement preventive measures, though further improvement progress is needed. Key recommendations include strengthening legal frameworks, integrating safety into farm management training, and increasing access to healthcare and safety resources. These actions aim to reduce occupational diseases and improve the long-term health and safety of agricultural workers.

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The Lithuanian agricultural advisory service: supporting farm workers' health and safety

Issue: Agriculture in Lithuania is a high-risk industry, with workers exposed to hazards such as heavy machinery and livestock. Despite regulations, the incidence of accidents and occupational diseases remains high. Small farms, in particular, struggle with the lack of resources to ensure adequate safety measures and training.

Method: The Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service (LAAS) provides specialised occupational safety services to farmers, including to small farms. LAAS offers consultations, risk assessments, and assistance in preparing safety documentation. The service is designed to help farmers comply with legal requirements, improve safety practices, and reduce risks of workplace accidents and health issues.

Results: LAAS has successfully supported farmers in understanding and managing occupational safety risks. By offering tailored services, LAAS helps ensure safer working conditions, reduce accidents, and improve farm productivity. Despite challenges, the initiative has highlighted the need for a broader, more dedicated focus on occupational safety within Lithuania's agricultural sector.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Poland

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: Agriculture is a vital sector of Poland's economy, yet accidents and occupational diseases in farming remain a significant challenge. The majority of farms are small and medium-scale, with over 90% of the agricultural land and the large animals owned by individuals. Although the number of reported accidents has declined, many incidents go unreported, leading to an underestimation of the problem.

Method: The Polish Community of Practice (CoP) analysed national literature, consulted experts, and reviewed findings from the COST Action SACURIMA project. Priority needs were identified through consultations with key stakeholders and interviews with farm safety experts, including representatives from The Agricultural Social Insurance Fund (ASIF), The Central Institute for Labour Protection (CILP), and The Nofer Institute of Occupational Medicine (NIOM). These consultations led to the development of three core challenges: inadequate safety education, limited access to health services, and the use of modern technologies to improve safety in agriculture.

Results: The CoP emphasised the need for systemic solutions in safety education, particularly from primary to higher education levels. It also highlighted the importance of improving access to health services and periodic medical examinations for farmers. Additionally, the adoption of modern technologies such as automation and AI could significantly enhance safety and wellbeing. Pilot projects are planned at the local level, with potential for national implementation, focusing on risk management and behaviour change to reduce accidents and occupational diseases.

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Target audience

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Target group 3: Researchers

Enhancing farm safety education

Issue: Despite efforts to improve occupational health and safety (H&S) in Poland's agricultural sector, farm-related accidents remain a concern. Many rural schools offer only limited education on farm safety, and children, often involved in farm work, are particularly at risk. There is a need to address this gap and implement a systemic approach to safety education across all school levels.

Method: The approach focuses on integrating farm health and safety education into the curriculum for rural primary, secondary, and agricultural schools. By collaborating with the State Labour Inspection, the Agricultural Social Insurance Fund, and other institutions, the proposal aims to provide consistent, age-appropriate safety training. Additionally, external educators such as agricultural advisors and local authorities will play a key role in delivering these lessons.

Results: The recommendation is to make H&S education mandatory across all rural schools, starting from primary level, with a focus on risk awareness for children. The integration of farm safety into existing curricula, alongside practical activities like competitions and workshops, can enhance awareness and encourage safer behaviour. This early education may also promote safer practices among farming families, benefiting both children and adults.

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Target audience

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Improving farmer health and health service access

Issue: Agriculture in Poland is associated with high health risks, including accidents and diseases caused by mechanical, biological, chemical, and physical factors. Despite these risks, occupational diseases are underdiagnosed, particularly allergic conditions and musculoskeletal disorders. Additionally, farmers often do not undergo regular health check-ups, resulting in late-stage diagnoses.

Method: This project advocates a comprehensive approach to improving farmers' health and safety, with a focus on education and policy reforms. Key measures include raising awareness about health risks, improving access to medical diagnostics, offering psychological support, and promoting periodic health examinations for farmers. A proposed solution is to introduce a system of farm replacements to ensure continuity of work during health-related absences.

Results: The introduction of health screening and greater medical support for farmers could lead to earlier disease detection and better overall wellbeing. Access to modern diagnostics and mental health support can reduce occupational hazards and enhance farmers' safety. Additionally, providing temporary replacements for farmers could improve their work-life balance and prevent burnout, contributing to long-term agricultural productivity.

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Technological improvements

Issue: Modern agricultural machinery and innovations, such as automation and artificial intelligence, significantly enhance productivity but also introduce new health and safety risks. The increased complexity of machinery and the mental strain on operators, especially older farmers, poses challenges to worker safety.

Method: This project examines the implementation of modern technologies, such as smart farming systems, automation, and digital tools, to improve farm work safety. The focus is on educating farmers, including through online platforms, simulators, and psychological support, to ensure proper use of new technologies. Smart digital monitoring systems, wearable devices, and tele-information systems are also explored to track and manage health and safety risks in real time.

Results: The use of modern technologies has improved farming safety by reducing physical strain and offering real-time alerts for hazardous conditions. However, challenges remain, such as the need for improved skills to operate advanced equipment and the potential psychological impact such retraining has on workers, particularly older generations. To fully realise the benefits, continuous education, safety protocols, and targeted solutions for smaller farms are essential. Further research and collaboration with technology providers will help address these challenges and improve overall occupational health and safety in Polish agriculture.

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Vision Zero: a farm safety good practice

Issue: Agricultural work in Poland has historically seen a high number of accidents and occupational diseases, partly due to the lack of legal health and safety regulations before 1990. Although preventive activities have been ongoing, participation is voluntary, which has sometimes led to lower engagement in safety initiatives.

Method: The Agricultural Social Insurance Fund (ASIF), in cooperation with various institutions like the State Labour Inspection (SLI), has implemented numerous preventive actions over the past 30 years. These include training, competitions, farm inspections, and distribution of safety equipment. In 2023, ASIF launched the “Safe Farmer, Safe Countryside” project, which integrates these efforts under a common logo and catchphrase, aiming to enhance prevention messages and support pre-medical rescue in rural areas.

Results: ASIF's initiatives have resulted in an 80% reduction in agricultural accidents from 1993 to 2023. The number of participants in educational activities has steadily increased, with over 115,000 farmers taking part in 2023. The introduction of the Vision Zero Strategy, focusing on preventing accidents and promoting wellbeing, has further bolstered these efforts. Looking forward, expanding voluntary participation through local facilitators and farm self-assessments is key to further enhancing safety on farms.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Romania

Health and safety needs in agricultura in Romania

Issue: In Romania, the agricultural sector faces significant health and safety challenges due to outdated equipment, poor working conditions, and a lack of inclusive health support. Additionally, there is a lack of accurate statistics on workplace accidents, making it difficult to address these issues effectively.

Method: The development of a Farm Safety and Health Needs Register aimed to systematically identify the specific needs of workers in Romanian agriculture, particularly in sheep farming. The register was based on both statistical data and qualitative input gathered from the SafeHabitus Community of Practice (CoP) through interviews and focus groups. It covers safety issues related to outdated equipment and the need for training, as well as health concerns linked to poor working conditions and socio-demographic factors.

Results: The register identified key areas requiring urgent attention, such as modernising equipment, improving working conditions, and addressing health risks, including mental health challenges. Recommendations include creating educational programmes, forming partnerships to implement safety measures, and enhancing policy to support farm workers. The CoP aims to use these findings to develop targeted solutions, drawing on national and international best practices improving safety and health in Romanian agriculture.

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Improved equipment enhances farming safety

Issue: In Romania, outdated farming machinery, particularly on sheep farms, presents significant health and safety risks. Old equipment, such as tractors and balers, often lacks modern safety features, increasing the likelihood of accidents. Many farmers attempt repairs without proper expertise due to financial constraints, further exacerbating the risks. Additionally, Romania lags behind the European Union in terms of agricultural mechanisation, which impacts both safety and economic efficiency.

Method: This issue was identified through analysis of statistical data and discussions within the SafeHabitus Community of Practice (CoP) in Romania, alongside interviews with farmers. The CoP highlighted the widespread use of old and malfunctioning machinery, which contributes to farm accidents, including fatalities.

Results: The findings stress the need for modern machinery with built-in safety features to reduce farm accidents. Recommendations include incorporating health and safety criteria into EU funding for farm mechanisation, promoting the retrofitting of existing equipment, and improving infrastructure for safe machinery operation and storage. It is also suggested that specialised training on modern farm technology be enhanced to improve safety and efficiency.

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Enhancing health and safety awareness in farming

Issue: In Romania, there is a significant gap in health and safety awareness within the agricultural sector, particularly in sheep farming. Many workers lack the knowledge needed to manage risks and maintain safety on farms. This is partly due to inadequate specialised education and limited access to relevant training on health and safety in agricultural work.

Method: The SafeHabitus Community of Practice (CoP) in Romania identified this issue through group discussions and highlighted the need for improvements at multiple levels of education. Key areas for intervention include enhancing the curricula in agricultural high schools and universities, providing continuous training for educators and trainers, and integrating health and safety into broader educational frameworks.

Results: To address these challenges, recommendations include revising educational curricula to include specific courses on occupational health and safety, investing in modern training facilities, and promoting collaborations with the private sector. In addition, general education in rural schools should raise awareness among young people about agricultural safety. Community-level campaigns and partnerships with healthcare professionals can further support these initiatives, ensuring that the agricultural workforce is better equipped to handle safety risks.

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Target group 3: Farmers, farm workers and others exposed to the farm environment

Labour force shortage in agriculture and its implications on the health of those working in the sector

Issue: Romanian agriculture, particularly in sheep farming, faces a severe labour shortage, exacerbated by low interest from the younger population and significant emigration from rural areas. This shortage leads to overwork, stress, and a lack of rest or medical care for farmers, which negatively impacts both their physical and mental health.

Method: Desk research and discussions within the SafeHabitus Community of Practice (CoP) highlighted the causes and effects of labour shortages in the sector. Two primary factors were identified: the unattractiveness of agricultural work due to poor conditions and low wages, and the high rate of emigration for seasonal work. Within this framework, the impact of these factors on the health of those working in agriculture was explored.

Results: To address these challenges, it is recommended that measures be taken to improve the attractiveness of agricultural work by providing better working conditions. Public authorities should provide support for seasonal migrants to ensure they are informed about their rights including aspects related to health protection and work safety. Social research should further explore the causes of labour shortages and seasonal migration, helping to design targeted interventions.

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Target group 3: Researchers

The Doctors' Caravan: supporting occupational health of farmers and rural communities

Issue: Access to healthcare in rural areas of Romania is limited due to insufficient healthcare infrastructure and a lack of medical professionals. This disparity results in a significant gap in life expectancy between rural and urban populations, with rural residents living on average three years less than those in cities.

Method: The identification of best practice models that can impact the health of farmers and farm workers, and a discussion on the potential for scaling up these models. The analysis of a mobile healthcare initiative, the Doctors' Caravan, shows us how this issue can be addressed by providing medical services directly to rural communities. Founded in 2014, the project focuses on health risk identification, prevention, and early disease detection. The caravan offers targeted medical services in areas such as paediatrics, women's health, and internal medicine.

Results: In 2023, the Doctors' Caravan reached 3,831 beneficiaries across 37 caravans, involving 417 volunteers. The initiative has successfully attracted partnerships with medical companies and public institutions, offering services like liver disease screening and the installation of defibrillators in rural villages. It has proven to be an effective way to deliver healthcare to vulnerable rural populations. To expand upon this good practice, it is recommended to form partnerships with farmers' associations and local authorities to improve access to healthcare for agricultural workers and their families.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Slovakia

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: In Slovakia, farmers often prioritise other concerns over farm health and safety (FHS), such as financial challenges, market fluctuations, and operational issues. The perception that FHS initiatives require significant time and resources may deter some farmers from being actively engaged in this matter. These barriers affect the adoption of safer farming practices and the overall health of farmers.

Method: The Slovak Community of Practice (CoP) initiated the development of a Farm Safety and Health Needs Register. Through discussions with relevant stakeholders, key risks and challenges were identified, including unsafe machinery, animal handling, wildlife threats and farmer health issues like musculoskeletal injuries and mental health concerns. The CoP focused on creating solutions that consider farmers' needs, infrastructure and equipment to improve safety and wellbeing.

Results: The Needs Register highlighted critical issues in both farm safety and farmer health, including the importance of training on machinery use, animal handling and wildlife management. It also emphasised the need for improved infrastructure, workload management and prevention strategies. The CoP's recommendations aim to bridge the gap between theoretical safety strategies and practical solutions, integrating cultural and occupational contexts. Future solutions will focus on effective training, raising awareness and developing preventive measures to ensure a safer, healthier farming environment.

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Transforming attitudes towards farm safety

Issue: In Slovakia, farmers often view farm health and safety (FHS) as a burden rather than a beneficial practice. Their focus on financial pressures, operational issues, and market fluctuations leaves little room for prioritising FHS, which affects productivity and worker wellbeing.

Method: To address this, the focus is on changing attitudes by highlighting the economic and practical benefits of FHS. This involves demonstrating how healthy, well-trained workers are more efficient and less likely to suffer injuries. Additionally, the need for targeted FHS education in schools, vocational training, and university programmes is identified, alongside the development of agriculture-specific regulations and guidelines. Awareness campaigns and practical demonstrations further support this shift.

Results: The recommended approach stresses integrating FHS into farm management, with a focus on its direct impact on farm productivity and economic viability. Raising awareness through accessible educational materials, tailored training, and policy development is crucial. To ensure lasting change, continuous engagement with stakeholders and studies on the effectiveness of safety measures will help improve both farm health and safety in Slovakia, fostering a more sustainable and productive farming environment.

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Enhancing machinery safety

Issue: In Slovakia, outdated agricultural machinery, poor maintenance practices, and lack of safety awareness contribute to high safety risks for farmers. Financial constraints and inadequate training further prevent many farmers from addressing these risks, leading to potential injuries and productivity losses.

Method: A comprehensive approach is needed to address machinery safety. This includes developing clear safety guidelines, offering targeted training on machinery operation and maintenance, and encouraging technological upgrades. Government-supported financial incentives and subsidies can help farmers replace outdated equipment. Integrating Farm Health and Safety (FHS) education into agricultural curricula ensures that future farmers are prepared for safe machinery handling.

Results: To improve machinery safety, Slovakia should enhance training accessibility, implement financial support for equipment upgrades, and strengthen regulatory oversight. Regular inspections and safety campaigns will help promote a culture of safety. By focusing on practical, education-based solutions, targeted financial assistance, and clearer safety regulations, Slovakia can reduce machinery-related accidents and ensure a safer and more productive agricultural sector. This approach promotes long-term safety and sustainability in Slovak farming.

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Enhancing animal handling safety

Issue: Animal handling in Slovakia poses significant safety risks due to insufficient training, improper techniques, and outdated equipment. Farm workers, often lacking agricultural education, face dangers like crush injuries, kicks, and accidents caused by unpredictable animal behaviour. These risks not only harm workers but also affect animal welfare and productivity.

Method: To address these challenges, it is essential to develop customised training programmes for farm workers. These should focus on safe handling techniques, animal behaviour, and stress reduction methods. In addition, financial support for infrastructure upgrades, such as improved handling pens and ergonomic tools, is necessary to ensure safer working conditions. Research into innovative technologies and the development of evidence-based guidelines for animal handling are also crucial.

Results: A comprehensive action plan should include the following measures which can enhance farm safety, improve animal welfare, and ensure sustainable agricultural practices in Slovakia.

1. Tailored training and collaboration with veterinary professionals.
2. Financial incentives for upgrading facilities and equipment.
3. Investment in research and innovation on animal welfare and handler safety.
4. Strengthened regulatory oversight and compliance with safety standards.
5. Knowledge-sharing platforms for best practices.

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Farm safety good practice: OHSAS podcasts and blogs

Issue: In Slovakia, agriculture remains a vital sector in the country's economy, yet farmers often overlook farm health and safety (FHS) due to other pressing concerns such as financial pressures. This can lead to unsafe working conditions and a lack of awareness about proper safety practices in the sector.

Method: OHSAS, a Slovak company specialising in occupational health and safety (OHS) assessments, has adopted a digital approach to raise awareness. Using podcasts and blogs, they provide accessible, practical advice on topics like safe machinery use, chemical handling, and emergency response mechanisms. The informal, conversational style of the podcasts helps engage farmers and make safety information more relatable.

Results: This initiative has begun to shift attitudes towards safety, with farmers increasingly recognising the importance of OHS practices. The blog offers detailed articles on specific safety measures, complementing the podcasts. Together, these platforms help farmers adopt better safety practices, enhancing overall health and safety standards. OHSAS's approach demonstrates the effectiveness of using modern communication tools to promote farm health and safety and could serve as a model for other sectors.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Slovenia

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: Family farms in Slovenia face numerous challenges, including health and safety risks, poor work-life balance and economic pressures. However, statistics on accidents, injuries and occupational diseases on farms are often incomplete, as they only take into account those who are covered by social insurance and neglect those who are not, such as pensioners and family members. This lack of comprehensive data hinders effective safety planning.

Method: The Slovenian Community of Practice (CoP) initiated a mapping exercise to identify the main health and safety issues on farms. CoP members, including experts and researchers, analysed available statistics and shared experiences to identify critical farm safety issues. They focused on the use of machinery, exposure to pesticides, mental health, and musculoskeletal problems. These findings were compiled into a needs register to address the challenges faced by farmers.

Results: The needs register revealed pressing issues such as machinery risks, unsafe working conditions, and farmers' mental health problems. The CoP recommended improved data collection, including for uninsured workers, and a greater focus on education, training and regular safety inspections. They also advocated for psychological support and farm relief services to alleviate stress and burnout. This comprehensive approach aims to improve the safety and wellbeing of farmers in Slovenia.

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Addressing farm machinery accidents

Issue: Slovenian farmers face significant risks, particularly due to machinery accidents and forestry related injuries. Despite efforts to improve safety, the number of accidents, especially fatal ones, remains high. This is compounded by a lack of comprehensive data, as many incidents involving non-socially insured workers (e.g. retirees, children, and casual workers) go unreported. There is also a worrying decrease in farm accident insurance coverage, which hinders the implementation of effective safety measures.

Method: The study analysed accident statistics from the National Institute of Public Health (NIJZ), police reports, and expert surveys to assess the scale of accidents on Slovenian farms. The analysis focused on machinery-related accidents and the need for improved safety measures, particularly in the forestry sector. It included consultations with Slovenian farming organisations, who shared their insights and proposed solutions.

Results: The results reveal that machinery accidents, especially with tractors and forestry equipment, remain the leading cause of fatalities. Recommendations include improving accident reporting to better reflect the true scale of the problem, enhancing safety training for farmers, and extending social security cover for farmers. Implementing sector-specific safety legislation and supporting ongoing safety campaigns, particularly for tractor safety and forest work, is also advised.

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Improving farming social security

Issue: Slovenian farmers face significant barriers to accessing social security, with many unable to meet the income thresholds required for compulsory insurance. This is exacerbated by the fact that they have limited knowledge of their rights and obligations. Female farmers in particular are more vulnerable due to their unpaid labour and lack of resources, leading to inadequate social security coverage and economic dependence on other family members.

Method: The study presents the challenges and needs of Slovenian farmers in terms of health and social security. The data were collected from various sources, including focus groups, surveys and consultations with farming organisations. The TERA project, which aimed to promote work-life balance and social security awareness among farmers, is an important example of a good intervention.

Results: Results show a significant gap in insurance coverage for farmers, especially women, who often lack adequate pension and maternity benefits. There is a clear need for increased awareness and support regarding farmers' rights, as well as policy reforms to improve access to insurance. Empowering local communities and facilitating cross-sectoral co-operation are essential for addressing these issues. Future efforts should focus on expanding farm relief services and improving social security education.

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Improving farmer mental health

Issue: Farm life in Slovenia is often characterised by stress, isolation and a range of personal and professional challenges, including financial pressures, weather uncertainties, and generational conflicts. These pressures contribute to farmers suffering from high levels of mental health problems such as burnout, stress, and exhaustion. Many farmers, especially those on family farms, struggle with mental health problems but often do not seek help due to stigmatisation and a lack of tailored services. Farmers' mental health needs are not sufficiently documented or supported by systemic structures.

Method: To better understand these challenges, several studies, including a 2021 survey and ongoing projects such as "POWER(less) of RURAL AREAS", have investigated the mental health of Slovenian farmers. These studies included both quantitative and qualitative approaches and showed that a significant proportion of farmers suffer from mental health problems. Gender and generational factors play a major role in these challenges.

Results: The surveys showed that Slovenian farmers urgently need customised support for their mental health. They showed a high rate of mental health problems, such as stress, fatigue, and sleep disorders. Despite the stigmatisation of mental health, some progress has been made with initiatives such as psychosocial counselling for family farms. Going forward, a comprehensive strategy is needed to monitor and address farmers' mental health, including regular research, professional development, and public awareness campaigns.

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Psychosocial counselling: a good practice for health and safety in agriculture

Issue: Farming is one of the most hazardous occupations, with a high rate of accidents, injuries and psychological stress. In Slovenia, 86% of farmers report being under significant stress, and the suicide rate among farmers is four times higher than the national average. This indicates the urgent need to address mental health in the agricultural sector.

Method: In 2021, the “NeMOČ PODEŽELJA” [(in)POWER OF RURAL AREAS] project was launched, bringing together the Slovenian Rural Youth Association, the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (abbreviated in Slovenian as ZRC SAZU), and other partners to improve the quality of life on farms. The project included workshops and surveys to understand the mental health challenges faced by farmers. In 2022, the Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia introduced a programme offering free psychosocial support, including counselling on mental health, succession and financial issues. This service is provided by a trained advisor familiar with the farming context.

Results: The first results of the aforementioned service show a significant need for mental health support, with 68% of farmers expressing interest in the service. The counselling sessions have led to an improvement in mental health, including better communication, less violence and less stress. The success of this initiative points to the need for similar services across Europe and it is recommended that funding and expansion continue.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: CoP Spain

Farmer health and farm safety needs

Issue: Migrant workers in the berry sector in Huelva face significant health and safety challenges. These workers are more prone to accidents due to harsh working conditions, language barriers, and limited access to health services. National statistics highlight a higher accident rate among migrant workers in agriculture, with severe consequences, including fatalities.

Method: A Needs Register was developed through interviews with key sector stakeholders, Community of Practice (CoP) meetings, and fieldwork within the SafeHabitus project. These activities provided insights into the specific health and safety challenges faced by migrant workers, focusing on ergonomics, access to healthcare, heat stress, chemical exposure, living conditions, and mental health.

Results: The findings identified several critical areas for improvement that could reduce risks and create a safer, healthier environment for migrant workers. Develop and implement ergonomic initiatives, including adjustable workstations, training workshops, and informational materials. Enhance access to healthcare, including clear information about local health services. Measures to prevent heat stress, like adjusted work schedules and shaded rest areas. Safe use of phytosanitary products, with better protective equipment and training. Improved living conditions and mental health support services.

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Addressing heat stress and sun exposure for migrant farmworkers

Issue: Workers in Huelva's berry industry face growing risks from heat stress and sun exposure. With high temperatures, especially in greenhouses, workers are at risk of heat stroke, dehydration, and long-term health problems. The impact of climate change worsens these conditions, presenting a challenge to worker safety and productivity.

Method: The Community of Practice (CoP) in Huelva identified key risks through discussions with stakeholders. Key issues include heat strokes, dehydration, and the impact of fasting during Ramadan. A variety of solutions were proposed to mitigate these risks, such as adjusting work schedules, improving workplace conditions, and providing proper training and personal protective equipment (PPE).

Results: Recommendations to address heat stress include starting work earlier to avoid peak heat hours, ensuring access to water, using lightweight PPE, and improving ventilation and shading in greenhouses. Middle management plays a critical role in implementing and monitoring these measures. Further research is needed to assess the impact of these practices on both worker wellbeing and productivity. Effective management of heat stress is vital for protecting workers and sustaining the industry.

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Improving migrant farmworkers' healthcare access

Issue: Migrant workers in Huelva, Spain, face significant barriers to healthcare access, including administrative obstacles, inadequate living conditions, and language and cultural challenges. Many workers, particularly women, struggle to access essential health services despite contributing to social security. The lack of infrastructure, transportation, and adequate support systems exacerbates their vulnerability, putting their health and safety at risk.

Method: This project identifies key barriers through consultations with stakeholders, including local organisations and migrant communities. It proposes specific interventions, such as improving access to health services in agricultural settlements, offering translation and intercultural mediation, and raising awareness about migrants' rights and healthcare access. A coordinated approach involving local authorities, employers, and community organisations is crucial.

Results: The project recommends extending the reach of health services to the migrant population, ensuring translation services in healthcare facilities, and promoting policies for administrative regularisation of migrants. Measures to improve living conditions, such as installing essential services (water, electricity, sanitation), are also vital. Active employer involvement and government support are critical to improving access to health services for migrant workers in Huelva.

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Improving farmworkers' housing conditions

Issue: Agricultural migrant workers in Huelva face severe housing challenges that compromise their health, safety, and wellbeing. The predominant housing types (on-farm accommodations and shantytown settlements) are overcrowded, unsanitary, and lack adequate infrastructure. These conditions are dangerous and include inadequate space, poor sanitation, and a lack of basic services such as clean water and electricity. The proximity to work limits access to external services, exacerbating the workers' vulnerability to labour exploitation and health risks.

Method: The identification and analysis of housing conditions in Huelva through discussions with members of the Spanish Community of Practice were carried out. Data were gathered on the living situations within farm accommodations and shantytown settlements, particularly in terms of overcrowding, infrastructure, and basic service availability. The research also highlights the broader social and economic issues faced by the migrant workers, including limited legal status and labour exploitation.

Results: Key findings show that improvements to migrant housing are minimal and enforcement of regulations is insufficient. Efforts to improve conditions on farms, including new habitability standards, have been inadequate. Similarly, current slum eradication efforts lack viable housing alternatives. The results call for stronger regulatory enforcement, more frequent inspections, and the construction of sustainable housing solutions that include access to basic services, as well as enhanced social inclusion initiatives.

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Providing dignified housing: A farm health and safety good practice

Issue: Migrant Farmworkers in Huelva face severe housing challenges and frequently live in overcrowded, unsanitary conditions in shantytowns made from waste materials. These settlements lack essential services such as clean water, electricity, and sanitation, leading to poor health and hygiene, increased disease risk, and legal vulnerability. Migrants also face the constant threat of forced eviction, contributing to insecurity and social exclusion.

Method: ASNUCI, a non-governmental organisation in Huelva, developed a shelter and day centre project to address these urgent housing needs. The facility, located in Lepe, offers shared rooms, collective bathrooms, a laundry service, a communal kitchen, and multifunctional common areas. It is designed to provide safe, hygienic living conditions and foster intercultural coexistence. The shelter operates on a self-management model, whereby residents ensure the facility's maintenance and upkeep.

Results: ASNUCI's project successfully offers safe housing for up to 40 migrants, along with essential services. The initiative also includes vocational training, Spanish language courses, and legal assistance to help migrants integrate themselves into Spanish society. This model has proven effective in improving living conditions and social inclusion and is scalable for replication in other regions facing similar challenges. However, greater support from public and private sectors is necessary to address the broader issue of migrant homelessness and exclusion.

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Target audience

Target group 1: Farmers, farm workers and others exposed to the farm environment

Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Non-governmental organisations (NGOs)

Contribution to expected outcomes and destination outcomes

The library of 56 Practice Abstracts presented in this document, and related 78 Technical Notes published in the SafeHabitus KnowledgeHub, are an important resource in their own right. They provide an overview of the social, economic, policy and governance context associated with farm safety and farmer health in 11 member states of the EU. In addition, this body of work contributes to the objectives that were set for the project, i.e. the Expected Outcomes and Destination Outcomes.

Expected outcomes

In line with key objectives set for the SafeHabitus project, research was undertaken as part of Work Package 2 to improve understanding and awareness of farmer and farm worker health and safety, and share bottom-up innovations. These activities contribute to key 'Expected Outcomes' that were established by the EU when the call for research proposals on the topic of working conditions in agriculture was published in 2022. In particular, the Practice Abstracts and Technical Notes support:

Outcome 1, *enhance understanding and awareness by policy makers, farmer's organisations, trade unions and health authorities of the potential solutions to the health and safety challenges faced by farmers and farm workers*, by providing a comprehensive description of the challenges, needs and potential solutions that will be disseminated through the SafeHabitus Knowledge Hub (Task 1.2), the National Policy Workshops (Task 2.4), the European Policy Forum (Task 6.2), and webinars and the SafeHabitus Summer School (Task 1.6).

Outcome 4, by identifying, documenting and sharing, via the mechanisms described for Outcome 1, innovative bottom-up initiatives, in particular dissemination of knowledge to key EU (Task 6.2) and national (Task 2.4) stakeholders, this work contributes to improving *health, safety and labour conditions in farming thanks to better performing European and national policy and legal frameworks and innovative bottom-up initiatives to support the implementation of the European Pillar of Social Rights and the EU's Farm to Fork strategy*.

Destination outcomes: Impact 1

The activities of the CoPs in identifying the environmental, socio-economic, behavioural, cultural and demographic context of safe/healthy or unsafe/unhealthy practices supports a better understanding of the drivers underpinning these (PAs 3-7 and TNs 1, 3 – 7). The MAA implemented by the CoP supports social innovation and the development or deployment of social and community-based innovations (PAs 3 -7 and TNs 2 – 7). This research and the associated dissemination activities contributes to the Destination Outcome, i.e. *Rural, coastal and urban areas are developed in a sustainable, balanced and inclusive manner thanks to a better understanding of the environmental, socio-economic, behavioural, cultural and demographic drivers of change as well as deployment of digital, nature-based, social and community-led innovations*.

Destination outcomes: Impact 2

The CoPs engage with and identify the safety and health needs of end-users including women, young people and vulnerable populations to ensure their needs are reflected in the development of innovations that promote social inclusion in the labour force (PAs 3 – 7 and TNs 1, 3 – 7). PAs presented in this report identify the needs of women, young people, including children, and vulnerable populations, including older workers and seasonal and migrant workers. These needs are considered from a range of perspectives including actions required to strengthen policy, service provision, industry and communities (inclusion). Farmers and farm workers of all ages and genders are empowered to

adopt health and safety protective innovations through their involvement in the co-design of these tools and the resources supporting their deployment. In developing this knowledge, the CoPs have empowered end users to highlight their needs and identify priorities that support good health and positive long-term prospects (PAs 3 – 6). Collectively this body of knowledge contributes to supporting *'good health and positive long-term prospects, including jobs, for all including women, young people and vulnerable groups'*.

Destination outcomes: Impact 3

The development, collation and sharing of Good Practices across the network of CoPs supports the identification of potential solutions that foster the innovation ecosystem necessary to translate these practices into services that meet local or national needs. Engagement within and networking between COPs reduces the perception and feeling of being left behind, even in the most remote locations. The geographical focus of CoPs varies with some adopting a community or regional focus whilst others concentrate on the national level. This reflects country-level differences in terms of both scale and governance, i.e. small countries with centralised governance systems tend to have a 'national' CoP, whilst larger member states with federal or strong regional governance systems tend to focus on the regional level CoP. This approach to identifying needs ensures that those living in remote areas or those more distant from national policy making processes are provided with a voice. Taken together, these actions support the achievement of *'Rural communities are equipped with innovative and smarter solutions that increase access to services, opportunities and adequate innovation ecosystems, including for women, youth and the most vulnerable groups, improve attractiveness and reduce the feeling of being left behind, even in the most remote locations like mountains'*.

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